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SCIENCE KNOWS NO BORDERS

ALLEA CONDEMNS PROPOSED RESTRICTIONS BY THE WHITE HOUSE ON INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH COLLABORATION

ALLEA strongly condemns the proposed U.S. Office of Management and Budget (OMB) rule published on 29 May 2026 ([Regulation for Federal Financial Assistance](#)). If implemented, it would impose significant barriers on international research collaboration, which is essential for scientific achievements and innovation. Moreover, by expanding political influence on research partnerships, with serious consequences for peer review, international cooperation and the autonomy of funding decisions, it is once more an attack on academic freedom.

Researchers must be able to choose collaborators solely on the basis of the added value of their scientific contribution. Measures that replace scholarly judgement with undefined political criteria would harm the reliability of science, limit or even abolish public trust in science, which is essential for policy advice – and a healthy democracy.

Science advances through the free exchange of ideas, knowledge, and expertise across borders. Restrictions on collaboration with vaguely defined “covered foreign entities” give rise to increasing protectionism with the risk of a chilling effect on, or even the cessation of, international partnerships. This undermines research excellence, innovation, and the global capacity to address shared challenges.

Academic freedom in the United States has, for a long time, been a role model and is an integral part of the global scientific ecosystem. Threats to this freedom will have repercussions far beyond national borders and therefore demands a collective response from the international research community.

You can read more about impact of the proposed OMB rule on academic freedom and international research cooperation in this [executive brief](#) by the Association of American Universities.

Call to action

The global scientific community must respond swiftly and collectively. A [public consultation](#) on the proposed rule is open until 13 July, providing a valuable opportunity to publicly demonstrate the collective stance of the global scientific community for open, international scientific cooperation, and to highlight the consequences these measures could have for research excellence, innovation, and the joint efforts to solve urgent problems. At a time when global challenges increasingly require global solutions, silence is not an option.

ALLEA calls on the global scientific community to respond collectively:

- **Research institutions, universities, academies, and research-funding organisations** should submit institutional responses, mobilise their networks, and coordinate evidence-based advocacy and policy advice across disciplines and borders.
- **National governments and EU policymakers** should engage with their U.S. counterparts and make clear that international scientific collaboration strengthens, rather than hinders, research excellence and competitiveness.
- **Individual researchers** should publicly share concrete examples of the benefits of international cooperation and the need to maintain open channels for scientific exchange and should flag examples where international research collaboration has been prevented, harmed, or cancelled.

About ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing 61 academies from 40 countries in Europe. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on the European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: <http://www.allea.org>.

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